

History of Chemistry in Australia 1788-1988

STANLEY LIVINGSTONE

Emeritus Professor of Inorganic Chemistry, The University of New South Wales, Kensington, N.S.W. 2033, Australia

The Establishment of the Colony of New South Wales

It was the Royal Society which was indirectly responsible for the European settlement of Australia.

The Society wished to send an expedition to Tahiti to observe the transit of Venus across the disc of the sun on 3 June 1769 "as the foundation for calculations which would determine the distance of the earth from the sun". The Society was able to obtain the cooperation of the Admiralty which chose as leader of the expedition Lieutenant James Cook, who was placed in command of the bark *Endeavour*. Cook set sail on 6 August 1768 with 85 persons on board, including an astronomer, Charles Green, and two botanists, Dr. D. C. Solander, FRS, "the ablest botanist in England", and Joseph Banks, FRS.

After successfully completing the astronomical observations in Tahiti, Cook followed the secret instructions given him by the Admiralty to seek in the south seas "a continent of land of great extent" which there was "reason to imagine" did exist. If he found it, Cook was to observe and report on its soil and precious metals, beasts, birds and plants, and its natives, and to take possession of it. Thus Cook's mission was scientific: to make observations on matters astronomical, geographical, botanical, zoological and anthropological. And Cook, the son of an illiterate Yorkshire farm labourer, was eminently capable of the weighty task given to him. He was elected a Fellow of the Royal Society in 1776 and the Society awarded him the Copley Medal for his paper read to the Society on the prevention of scurvy.

In 1779 Banks, now President of the Royal Society, recommended Botany Bay to a committee of the House of Commons as a suitable site for a penal colony. Lord Sydney, the Home Secretary, persuaded Prime Minister Pitt to accept the proposal. There is no evidence that either Pitt or Sydney designed to build a new Britain in the Antipodes. If they had, they would scarcely have wished to lay the foundation in crime. Rather Pitt helped to found Australia in a fit of absence of mind. As a consequence of their decision, on 13 May 1787 Captain Arthur Phillip, in command of 11 vessels carrying 717 convicts and some 400 officers, marines and sailors, left Portsmouth bound for New South Wales and arrived in Botany Bay on 18 January 1788. Phillip, considering the site unsuitable, moved his ships northwards into Port Jackson and established his settlement at Sydney Cove.

Early Colonial Science and Technology

While Phillip was establishing his colony, Lavoisier in France was laying the foundations of modern chemistry. But it was not until 1808 when Dalton in England published his *New System of Chemical Philosophy* that chemistry took on its modern form and the next half century saw great advances in the science of chemistry.

The early arrivals in the colony were convicts and naval and military personnel, along with a few free settlers. Few had any knowledge of agriculture, let alone any scientific knowledge or training. One exception was Dr. White, the Surgeon-General. His supplies of oil of peppermint soon became exhausted; this substance was much used at the time as a remedy for "gouty and cholicky pains and disorders arising from wind". White found an effective substitute in the oil distilled from the native tree *Eucalyptus piperita*, stating that he found it more satisfactory than the English product. He was thus the first to investigate the essential oils of Australian plants.

In 1815 James Dickson set up a steam engine in Sydney to grind wheat, pulverise tanning bark and saw timber. In 1827 he and his partner, John Mackie, established a "steam engine brewery" and sold "potent ale" at one shilling and sixpence a gallon. In September 1842 the Australasian Sugar Company began refining raw sugar. The following year Edward Knox became manager; his methods were empirical and he remarked that "there was no book on sugar analysis in the English language". In 1855 the company became the Colonial Sugar Refining Company but it was not until 1879 that it employed a chemist. Yet it was one of the first care sugar manufacturers in the world to apply the science of chemistry.

Records show that in 1848 there were in the colony of New South Wales 223 flour mills, 2 distilleries, 51 breweries, 30 soap and candle works, 62 tanneries, 27 foundries, 7 rope works, 5 salt works, and 4 hat factories. However, it was not until the gold rush of the early 1850's that there was any demand for people with a knowledge of geology, assaying, or chemical analysis.

It is noteworthy that the earliest heavy chemical industry was established by the Elliott brothers who commenced manufacturing sulphuric and nitric acids in Sydney in 1862 to supply the needs of a rapidly burgeoning agriculture. The first municipal gasworks in New South Wales were established in Bega about 1885 but no series attempts to utilise

coal tar as a raw material were made until 1930 when Timbrol's in Sydney initiated such work.

The Royal Society of New South Wales

At two meetings on 27 June and 4 July 1821 Messrs Bowman, Douglass, Field, Goulburn, Oxley and Wollstonecraft formed the Philosophical Society of Australasia. They expressed the need for such a society in the following words :

"Upwards of thirty years have elapsed since the colony of New South Wales was established in one of the most interesting parts of the world Yet little has been done to awaken a spirit of research or excite a thirst for information among the colonists...It is therefore proposed to form a Society for the purpose of collecting information with respect to the natural state, capabilities, productions and resources of Australasia and the adjacent regions, and for the purpose of publishing, from time to time, such information as may be likely to benefit the world at large".

A few months later Governor Brisbane encouraged the infant Society and accepted office as its President. Brisbane was an amateur astronomer and brought with him equipment and a competent astronomer, Dr. Charles Rumker. Brisbane, at his own expense, established an observatory at Parramatta. On 13 March 1822 Rumker read one of the first papers to the Society, entitled "On the Astronomy of the Southern Hemisphere". Other papers dealt with geology, geography, and ethnology but none dealing with chemistry is mentioned in the records.

Between 1823 and 1850 the Philosophical Society was replaced by a succession of others, formed to improve agriculture or horticulture, achieving moderately large memberships. In 1850 Dr. Henry Douglass, the Honorary Secretary of the Philosophical Society (1821-22), succeeded in reviving the original Society under the name of the Australian Philosophical Society with the stated aim of "the encouragement of Arts, Sciences, Commerce and Agriculture in Australia". The revived Society was active for a time but ceased to function during the turmoil of the gold rush but was again revived in 1855. In 1866 it became the Royal Society of New South Wales; its President was the Governor, Sir John Young with the Rev. William Clarke, "the pioneer geologist of Australia", as Vice-President. In 1868 the Society began publishing its own journal, viz. *Journal and Proceedings of the Royal Society of New South Wales*, which has enjoyed an uninterrupted annual publication to the present day.

The work of Douglass and Clarke for the Society and science in general in New South Wales was continued after Clarke's death by Professor Archibald Liversidge, who was appointed to the Chair of Chemistry in the University of Sydney in 1882. In 1886 he suggested the establishment of a federation or association of the 38 scientific bodies then extant in Australia and suggested ways by

which the Society might bring this into operation. He proposed the formation of an Australasian Association for the Advancement of Science, which actually occurred in 1888, Sydney's Centenary Year. The first meeting took place on 27 August-5 September 1888 in the University of Sydney with an attendance of 805 members and 45 ladies. The programme had ten sections with Chemistry and Mineralogy as Section B. The president of Section B was Professor J. G. Black of the University College of Otago, Dunedin, N.Z., who addressed the section "On Chemistry in Relation to Education".

The Royal Society of New South Wales played an important rôle in bringing scientists from many disciplines together. Its journal for many years was a medium of publication for geologists, chemists, astronomers and other scientists, particularly in regard to research of especial relevance to Australia. With the advent of specialist societies and, more recently, in the chemical field, of Divisions-relating to separate chemical sub-disciplines-within the Royal Australian Chemical Institute, the umbrella rôle of the Royal Society of New South Wales has virtually disappeared but it still continues as a viable organisation.

The University of Sydney

It was Dr. Douglass, Foundation Secretary of the Philosophical Society, who in 1848 put forward the idea of establishing a university in Sydney. A bill to endow The University of Sydney received the assent of Governor Sir Charles Fitzroy on 1 October 1850. It was decided to appoint initially only Professors of Classics, Mathematics, and Chemistry and Experimental Physics. There were 13 candidates for the Chair of Chemistry and Experimental Physics. The successful candidate was John Smith, AM, MD, aged 30, of Marischal College, Aberdeen, who "had greatly distinguished himself when a student in the Faculty of Arts, gaining various prizes, among others the highest in Natural History, Mathematics and Natural Philosophy and distinguished himself similarly in the Faculty of Medicine and had been much devoted to the science of chemistry and analytical researches therein". Upon his arrival in Sydney in September 1852, Smith commenced work in the basement of what is now Sydney Grammar School near Hyde Park. The University of Sydney formally began instruction with 24 matriculated students on 11 October 1852, offering only the degrees of BA and MA. For the Bachelor degree seven subjects had to be taken, viz. Latin, Greek, Mathematics, Natural Philosophy, Chemistry, Experimental Physics, and Logic.

Among Smith's many interests was the new art of photography. He used the "wet plate" technique and took photographs of scenes on the goldfields, harbour views, portraits, and the construction of the University's Gothic buildings. Several hundred of his negatives were discovered, after a lapse of 100 years, in the School of Chemistry at the

University and are now preserved in the archives. Smith became deeply involved in Sydney's water supply and education generally. In 1865, because of his many commitments, Smith applied for an assistant. In April 1866 the University appointed Alexander Thomson, BA, BSc, as Reader in Geology and Mineralogy and Assistant in the Laboratory. Thomson died in 1871, aged 30, and was replaced by Archibald Liversidge, who had been Demonstrator in Chemistry at Cambridge. Liversidge arrived in Sydney when an expansion of chemical and scientific activities was beginning in the colony; he soon became involved in research.

In 1874 Liversidge became Professor of Geology and Mineralogy, although he continued to hold the position of Demonstrator in Practical Chemistry until 1880. Smith continued as Professor of Chemistry and Experimental Physics until 1882, when his title was changed to Professor of Experimental Physics and Liversidge became Professor of Chemistry and Mineralogy. Smith died in 1885. He had served the University, science and education well as Australia's first Professor of Chemistry. He deserves to be ranked highly among Australia's pioneers.

Due to the efforts of Smith and Liversidge "after Homeric battles with the powerful forces of Arts" a separate Faculty of Science was established in 1885. Liversidge became the first Dean of the new Faculty. It is interesting to note that Smith and Liversidge were involved in an important development at Sydney University, viz. the admission of women students. The first woman to be awarded the BSc degree was Miss Fanny Hunt in 1888. Liversidge continued active in research and published over 100 papers. He retired in 1907 and returned to England, where he continued to work in the Davy-Faraday Laboratory at the Royal Institution, London. His work was widely recognised; no less than 13 universities and scientific bodies gave him honorary degrees or memberships. He died in 1927, aged 79.

Liversidge was replaced as Professor of Chemistry by Charles Fawsitt (1878–1960), a pupil of Ostwald. In 1913 the University established a Chair of Organic Chemistry with Professor (later Sir) Robert Robinson as the first occupant.

The University of Melbourne

The University of Melbourne was founded in 1853. Instruction in chemistry was begun in 1857 by Frederick McCoy, Professor of Geology and Mineralogy. However, it was not until 1882 that John D. Kirkland was appointed to the first Chair of Chemistry. Kirkland died in 1885 and was succeeded in 1886 by David Orme Masson from Edinburgh, who occupied the Chair until 1924.

Masson did much to raise the status of chemistry, not only in Melbourne but in Australia as a whole. In his inaugural address in March 1887 he stated: "A *School of Chemistry*! That is what it should

be; not a mere adjunct to one particular technical training but a school permeated by the atmosphere of research". In 1898 Masson undertook the earliest research work in Australia on coordination chemistry. A paper entitled "The Blue Salt of Fehling's Solution and Other Cuprotartrates" by Masson and Steele was published in the *Journal of the Chemical Society* in 1899. Masson's research student Bertrand Steele became the Foundation Professor of Chemistry in the University of Queensland. In 1920 Masson put his research students, Packer and Wark, to work on cuprotartrates, the problem on which he and Steele had worked 22 years before. Ian, later Sir Ian, Wark was to become one of Australia's most distinguished scientists and John Packer in 1944 was appointed to the Chair of Chemistry at Canterbury University College, Christchurch.

David Rivett was appointed Professor of Chemistry upon Masson's retirement in 1924. He resigned in 1926 to join the Executive of the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research, later known as CSIRO. In 1928 E. J. Hartung was appointed to the Chair of Chemistry.

The University of Adelaide

The University of Adelaide was founded in 1874, and in 1885 Edward H. Rennie was appointed Foundation Professor of Chemistry, the first Australian-born occupant of a chair of chemistry. Rennie was born in Sydney in 1852. His father was Auditor-General for New South Wales and his grandfather had been Professor of Zoology at Kings College, London. He was educated at Sydney Grammar School, where he was Captain and Knox Prizeman in 1867.

Rennie entered Sydney University in 1868 and in 1869 he shared Professor Smith's Prize for Chemistry. He graduated BA in 1870 at the age of 18 and was appointed a teacher at Sydney Grammar School. He obtained his MA in 1876 and the following year went to London, where he was a Demonstrator in Chemistry at St. Mary's Hospital Medical School. Subsequently he worked at University College and was awarded the DSc degree by London University in 1881 and was made a Fellow of the Institute of Chemistry. He was given research grants by The Chemical Society to investigate Australian flora. After his appointment in Adelaide, Rennie continued his research on Australian plants. He gained a reputation as a very thorough teacher, lecturing on all aspects of chemistry. He held many important offices, being Acting Vice-Chancellor, Chairman of the School of Mines, President of ANZAAS, and Federal President of the Australian Chemical Institute. He died in 1927, aged 74. In 1931 the Australian Chemical Institute established the Rennie Memorial Medal to be awarded annually to the member of the Institute, under 33 years of age, who has contributed most to some branch of chemistry.

Rennie established a tradition of organic chemical research in Adelaide which was continued by his successors Professor A. K. McBeth and Professor G. M. Badger.

Mention must be made of Sir William Bragg and his son W. L., later Sir Laurence Bragg. William Bragg was appointed Professor of Mathematics in Adelaide in 1885. In 1907 he was made a Fellow of the Royal Society for his work on radioactivity. He left Adelaide in 1907 to become Professor of Physics in the University of London and in 1923 he was appointed Fullerton Professor of Chemistry at the Royal Institution and Director of the Davy-Faraday Research Laboratory, thus having the unique distinction of occupying Chairs of Mathematics, Physics and Chemistry. His son, Sir Laurence Bragg was born in Adelaide in 1890. In 1915 father and son were conjointly awarded the Nobel Prize for Physics for their pioneering work on X-ray crystallography. In 1919 Laurence Bragg succeeded Sir Ernest Rutherford as Langworthy Professor of Physics at Manchester.

Sydney Technical College

Technical education in New South Wales can be said to have begun in 1865 when the Sydney Mechanics School of Arts—founded in 1833—commenced classes in mechanical drawing. In 1869 the first series of science lectures was held in the School of Arts premises in Pitt Street and in 1871 chemistry lectures were inaugurated. They were given by Edward Rennie, a teacher at Sydney Grammar School, who has been already mentioned.

In 1878 William Dixon was appointed full-time Lecturer in Chemistry at the newly established Sydney Technical College. He had worked as an industrial chemist in Scotland and migrated to Australia, where he established himself in practice in Sydney as an analytical chemist and assayer. He acted as an examiner in chemistry at the University of Sydney. In 1892 he introduced a Diploma course in Chemistry. In the Sydney Technical College Calendar in 1895 it is stated: "Complete instructions can be imparted in every branch of chemistry bearing on arts, industries, or manufactures, and aid given in original research". Dixon remained at the Technical College until 1896 and died in 1917. He was one of the founders of the North Shore Gas Company.

Henry Smith enrolled as a student at Sydney Technical College in 1888. He became interested in the investigation of the chemical constituents of the essential oils of the eucalypts and in 1898 was appointed Assistant Curator and Economic Chemist at the Technological Museum in Ultimo, a position he held until his retirement in 1921. He was the pioneer of Australian phytochemistry. His Presidential Address to the Sydney Technical College Chemical Society in 1915 entitled "the National Value of the Chemical Effort" stressed the importance of chemical research and its application from

the national point of view. He is remembered by the H. G. Smith Memorial Medal which is awarded annually by the Royal Australian Chemical Institute to the Institute member who has contributed most to the development of some branch of chemical science, as judged by his research work published during the previous ten years. It is the Institute's most prestigious award.

During the ANZAAS meeting in 1912 Richard Challinor and Archibald Olle suggested that a chemical society be formed. And at a reunion dinner of past and present students on 5 April 1913 it was formally agreed that the Sydney Technical College Chemical Society be inaugurated. The first meeting was held on 2 August 1913. The Society continues as the University of New South Wales Chemical Society and is the oldest chemical society in New South Wales.

In 1915 a young American, Dr. Robert Murphy, was appointed Head of the Chemistry Department at Sydney Technical College, a position he held for 32 years. In 1917 he upgraded the Chemistry Diploma course, extending it from four part-time years to five, and introduced the Chemical Engineering Diploma course—the first chemical engineering course in Australia. He constructed his courses to meet the needs of the chemical industry in New South Wales at the time. In 1924 the Chemistry and Chemical Engineering Diplomas were recognised as a qualification for Associateship of the Royal Institute of Chemistry of Great Britain.

In 1952 the newly established University of Technology (later the University of New South Wales) took over the Chemistry and Chemical Engineering Diploma courses from Sydney Technical College and established degree courses in Applied Chemistry, Chemical Engineering, and Metallurgy. In 1959 the Diploma courses were abolished.

Other Tertiary Institutions

The Universities of Sydney, Melbourne, and Adelaide are the oldest in Australia. Others followed: Tasmania (1890), Queensland (1909), Western Australia (1911), Australian National University (1946) and New South Wales (1949). Between 1954 and 1974 another eleven were established. All have viable Schools of Chemistry as do the NSW University of Technology and a number of Institutes of Technology.

The Royal Australian Chemical Institute

The Society of Chemical Industry of Victoria was founded in 1900 by Professor David Orme Masson of the University of Melbourne. At a meeting of the Society on 17 July 1916 Masson moved: "that in the opinion of the Council it is desirable that an Association or Institute of Chemists be formed in Australia, having for its objects: (i) to guarantee the professional qualifications of its members; (ii) to improve the status of the

profession; (iii) to secure for its practitioners adequate emoluments for their services”.

The resolution was carried and Masson came to Sydney the following week and prevailed upon Professor Fawsitt, Head of the Chemistry Department at the University of Sydney, to convene a meeting of representative chemists in Sydney on 20 July 1916 to hear Masson's views on the proposal to form an Australian Institute of Chemistry. At this meeting it was agreed that those present should constitute themselves as a provisional committee for New South Wales with Mr. B. J. Smart as Honorary Secretary; later Dr. Thomas Cooksey became Chariman. Subsequently, provisional committees were formed in Victoria, South Australia and Western Australia. A conference was held in Sydney on 10 January 1917 attended by representatives from three states, viz. Dr. Cooksey (NSW), Professor Masson (Vic), and Professor Rennie (SA). This Central Committee drew up a draft constitution for the proposed Institute.

At a meeting at the Royal Society's House, Sydney, on 18 June 1917 the Australian Chemical Institute was founded and the constitution was ratified. Dr. Murphy moved that a Branch of the Institute be formed in Sydney and the motion was carried. The first meeting of the Institute's Council was held at the Royal Society's House, Sydney, on 8–9 January 1918 with Dr. Cooksey in the Chair. The 50th Jubilee of the NSW Branch was celebrated at dinner, attended by Dr. Murphy, at the Wentworth Hotel, Sydney in June 1967.

In 1921–22 discussions were held with the Australian Association of Chemists and Metallurgists (founded in Lithgow). The Association was competing with the newly formed Institute in claiming to represent professional chemists, many of whom had no formal qualifications and feared that the Institute would not recognise their members as professionals. It was agreed that the Association would disband and the Institute would recognise bonafide practising chemists who were not academically qualified.

In 1932 the Institute was granted a Royal Charter, which inter alia, confers on Corporate Members the right to use the title Chartered Chemist (Australia). The Institute represents all branches of the profession of chemistry and is thus able to take a broad view of the professional scene. It is the qualifying body for professional chemists in Australia and the admission standards are recognised by all employers. Graduate membership is available to those who possess the minimum academic qualifications required for Associate membership. Associateship is granted following at least four years approved professional experience after satisfying the minimum academic requirements. Fellowship is awarded in recognition of a position of eminence in the profession.

In 1988 the Institute's membership included some 7800 professional chemists, chemical techno-

logists, chemical engineers and biochemists. The Institute has Branches in each state and the ACT. The corporate membership of the New South Wales branch is 2343. To serve the particular interests of its members the Institute has 12 Divisions, viz. Analytical Chemistry, Cereal Chemistry, Chemical Education, Colloid and Surface Chemistry, Electrochemistry, Industrial Chemistry, Inorganic Chemistry, Medicinal and Agricultural Chemistry, Organic Chemistry, Physical Chemistry, Polymer Chemistry, and Solid State Chemistry. All the Divisions hold national conferences at regular intervals.

The Chemical Industry during the Second World War

Early chemical industry in Australia was mainly concerned with the production of mineral acids essential to the manufacture of fertilisers for agriculture and explosives for mining. During the First World War the Australian chemical industry was not highly developed except in the field of metal extraction.

In the period between the two world wars chemical industry was largely concentrated in Sydney, Melbourne, Newcastle and Wollongong. There was a rapid growth during the thirties with developments in the manufacture of plastics, dyestuffs and drugs.

In June 1940 the control and supply of all metals and heavy chemicals were placed in the hands of the Directorate of Mineral Supply. The BHP Company had a monopoly of the iron and steel industry, and non-ferrous metal production was dominated by the “Collins House Group”. The heavy chemical industry was largely in the hands of the ICIANZ Company. The stimulus of war did much to spur on the development of scientific methods for the extraction of minerals. Examples are the use of floatation methods and magnetic separation. During the war the Australian chemical industry, largely centred in New South Wales and Victoria, expanded from 238 factories to 362, while the value of the output increased from 7 to 19 million pounds. One example is Timbrols Ltd of Rhodes, which by 1930 was exploiting coal tar—a by-product of the steel industry—to produce phenol, pyridine and other organic chemicals. In 1940 the company was asked by the government to produce aniline and two of its derivatives in large quantities needed for the manufacture of explosives. Full scale operation was achieved by April 1942.

In 1942 the Directorate of Manpower assessed the demand for engineers and scientists. The shortage of physicists was serious but the shortage of chemists was not so acute. However, there was a deficiency of chemical engineers and men trained at the higher technological levels. Little could be done to train them at short notice. The Central Chemical Advisory Committee was established at the head office of the Royal Australian Chemical

Institute in Melbourne; its task was to assess the types of chemists likely to be in short supply. Approximately 200 science students with a chemistry major graduated throughout Australia in 1942; about half went into munitions factories and most of the remainder went into private industry. A complete registration ordered by the Director-General of Manpower showed that in mid-1944 there were 4640 chemists, 4874 pharmacists, and 18383 engineers working in Australia.

CSIRO

The origins of CSIRO go back to 1916, when the Prime Minister, Billy Hughes, called together a number of prominent industrialists and scientists, including Masson, in order to discuss the formation of a scientific research institution to work on problems affecting primary and secondary industry. The Advisory Council for Science and Industry was created to suggest ways of setting up a permanent institute. The Council drafted a scheme but in 1917 political support lapsed and it was not until 1926 that the Bruce Government passed an Act setting up the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research.

The first Chairman was George, later Sir George, Julius and the first Chief Executive Officer was Professor, later Sir David, Rivett, who resigned his Chair of Chemistry in Melbourne to accept the post. At first the emphasis was on problems related to agriculture and forestry but in 1936 the activities of CSIR were extended to provide scientific assistance to secondary industry. The Division of Industrial Chemistry was formed in March 1940 with Dr. Ian Wark as Head.

Wark was born in 1899 and graduated from the University of Melbourne in 1923 and gained his PhD at University College, London working with Professor Donnan on coordination compounds of copper. He spent some time in Bragg's laboratory learning about X-ray crystallography and spent a year with G. N. Lewis at Berkeley, California. He then spent a year as Lecturer in Chemistry at the University of Sydney. In 1926 he became a research chemist at the Electrolytic Zinc Company in

Melbourne. In 1929 he became interested in surface chemistry and floatation processes for sulphide ores. His book *Principles of Floatation*, published in 1938, won international acclaim.

The Division of Industrial Chemistry was housed in laboratories at Fisherman's Bend, Melbourne. A decision was made to concentrate initially on non-metallic minerals and their utilisation, metals and alloys, hides and leather, and dairy produce.

CSIRO was virtually the only employer of top chemistry graduates during the Second World War. The universities were in decline, as staff were diverted to the war effort. Sir Alan Walsh, the pioneer of atomic absorption spectroscopy, wrote of the exciting intellectual climate of the early post-war years. In 1958 the Division of Industrial Chemistry was reorganised into six independent groups. Table 1 lists the Divisions related to chemistry in the period 1940–80.

TABLE 1—CSIRO DIVISIONS RELATED TO CHEMISTRY 1940–80

Division	Established	First Head
Industrial Chemistry	1940 ^a	Ian Wark
Physical Chemistry	1959 ^b	Keith Sutherland
Mineral Chemistry	1959	Richard Thomas
Chemical Physics	1958	Albert Rees
Applied Organic Chemistry	1961 ^b	James Price
Chemical Engineering	1962	Henry Pratt
Applied Chemistry	1966	Sefton Hamann
Chemical Technology	1974	Donald Weiss

^aSubdivided in 1958 into Physical Chemistry, Mineral Chemistry, and Chemical Physics.

^bAmalgamated in 1966 to form Applied Chemistry, which in 1974 was divided to form Applied Organic Chemistry and Chemical Technology.

Table 2 lists five notable development made by CSIRO in the chemical field.

Mineral Deficiency in Pastures :

"Coast disease" or "wasting disease" had been reported in sheep on Kangaroo Island and in south-eastern South Australia and also near Denmark in Western Australia. In these areas the rainfall was adequate and the pastures were often lush but the

TABLE 2—SOME NOTABLE DEVELOPMENTS BY CSIRO IN THE CHEMICAL FIELD

Sl. no.	Development	Principal	Division	Year
1.	Mineral deficiency wasting disease	H. Marston	Animal Nutrition	1984-
2.	Evaporation control	W. W. Mansfield	Physical Chemistry	1958-
3.	Atomic absorption spectroscopy	A. Walsh	Chemical Physics	1952-
4.	PSZ - the wonder ceramic	Advanced Materials Laboratory	Materials Science	1982-
5.	'Molecularly designed' low toxicity pesticides	G. Holan	Applied Organic Chemistry	1986-

sheep, especially the lambs, were lethargic, lost their appetite and often died.

In 1934 Dick Thomas, a chemist, and Hedley Marston, a biologist, in the CSIR Division of Animal Nutrition in Adelaide, traced the cause to a deficiency of cobalt and found that the sheep, if given 1 mg of cobalt nitrate per day, made a complete recovery. Later in 1934 Eric Underwood, of the Western Australian Department of Agriculture, tried the cobalt treatment on the affected sheep in Western Australia and effected a cure. Underwood later became a member of the CSIRO Executive and an international authority on trace metals in the diet. After more than 20 years Marston in 1954 proposed that a vitamin B₁₂ deficiency in sheep, caused by lack of cobalt, depressed their appetite, which further lowered their cobalt intake.

Evaporation Control :

Many farm dams in Australia and the south-western United States are located where the evaporation loss amounts to two metres per year. Bill Mansfield, of the Division of Physical Chemistry, over the period 1953–72 developed what was called the Mansfield Process, which cut this loss by at least 25 per cent. The process involves spreading a thin film of hexadecanol over the surface of the water. It proved satisfactory for farm dams up to 2 acres (approx. 1 ha) in area. Mansfield and R. G. Vines adapted the process for use on large reservoirs, where up to 50 percent reduction in evaporation loss was achieved in calm weather.

Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy :

Sir Alan Walsh of the Division of Chemical Physics had worked for years to perfect a spectroscopic method for the determination of small amounts of metals. In 1952 he made a breakthrough by measuring the absorption spectrum of the atomic vapour of the metal to be estimated. In simple terms the process works as follows. A flame produces atomic vapours from a sample. A lamp of the particular element to be estimated (e.g., a sodium lamp) irradiates the vapour and a detector records the radiation absorbed by the vapour. Elements can be determined in minute amounts in samples of soil, blood, urine, minerals or even wine. It has been said that Walsh's discovery is "the most significant advance in chemical analysis this century".

PSZ Ceramic :

PSZ, partially stabilised zirconia, is the toughest ceramic yet developed. It was developed in 1982 by the Division of Materials Science. PSZ has remarkable tensile strength over a range of temperatures and is not brittle like other advanced ceramics. It has other desirable engineering properties, including high thermal shock resistance, low thermal conductivity and exceptional wear resistance. PSZ is suitable, inter alia, for extrusion dies for copper tubing and for diesel engine cam followers.

Low toxicity Agricultural Chemicals :

The Division of Applied Organic Chemistry has recently developed highly selective, low toxicity pesticides and herbicides with, it is claimed, no long-term environmental effects. CSIRO has entered into an agreement with Du Pont to manufacture these chemicals for the world market. Underlying the research is some very original work by George Holan on molecular design of compounds having the desired properties and selective toxicity.

The Australian Atomic Energy Commission

The Australian Atomic Energy Commission was established in 1953 in a period of rapid development of the peaceful uses of atomic energy and when uranium was in great demand. Its aims are as follows: (i) To promote the search for mining and treatment of uranium, (ii) To develop practical uses of atomic energy, and (iii) To collect and distribute information on uranium and atomic energy.

In 1958 Professor Baxter, Vice-Chancellor of the University of New South Wales, became Chairman and tackled the job with his usual zeal and efficiency. In 1958 the atomic reactor was in operation at Lucas Heights, south of Sydney. Here a wide range of isotopes are produced for medical, scientific, and industrial purposes, and for export.

The Australian Institute of Nuclear Science and Engineering was established in 1959 to collaborate with universities on appropriate research programmes. In 1969 the Commonwealth and New South Wales Governments asked the Commission to carry out a feasibility study on the proposal to erect a nuclear power plant at Jervis Bay. In 1971 the Federal Government deferred a decision to proceed and in 1972 the matter was shelved indefinitely. In my opinion, this was a short-sighted attitude of the Government.

In 1987 the Australian Nuclear Science and Technology Organisation was established and took over the responsibilities of the Atomic Energy Commission. Its first Chairman was Professor R. E. Collins, Professor of Applied Physics at Sydney University. The number of staff, which has varied little in 20 years, is listed in Table 3.

TABLE 3—AUSTRALIAN NUCLEAR SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY ORGANISATION STAFF IN 1987

Professional	970
Technical	317
Trades	201
Administrative	238
Total	1026

Four Notable Australian Chemists

I should not like to finish this presentation without mentioning four outstanding Australian chemists. Their names are Adrien Albert (1907-),

Professor of Medical Research, ANU (1949–73); Frank Dwyer (1910–62), Senior Lect., Sydney Univ. (1946–55); Professor of Bioinorganic Chemistry, ANU (1955–62); Sir Ronald Nyholm (1917–71), Assoc. Prof. Univ. NSW (1953–55), Professor of Chemistry, University College, London (1955–71); Keith Sutherland (1916–78), Head, Division of Physical Chemistry, CSIRO (1956–58), Director, CSR Research Ltd. (1969–78), Chairman, NSW Committee, CSIRO (1967–78). I met Adrien Albert only twice but I knew the other three exceptionally well and regarded them as friends. Time does not permit me to dilate on their achievements. All did a great deal for Australian chemical science.

The Period 1945–1988—An Overview

During the Second World War the absence of certain important industries was keenly felt, e.g. aluminium and tin plate manufacture. A tin plate mill was established at Port Kembla in 1955 and aluminium ingot manufacture commenced at Bell Bay, Tasmania in the same year. Aluminium is now also produced in New South Wales and Queensland. The manufacture of pharmaceuticals and plastics has greatly expanded since the war.

The successful application of science during the war created an impression on the community and heightened its appreciation of the need for science. The successful launching of the first sputnik by the Soviet Union in October 1957 intensified the public's awareness of the need to train an adequate number of scientists with the result that research and tertiary education received much more generous government support than they had obtained hitherto.

New tertiary institutions were established. The first was the New South Wales University of Technology—later to become the University of New South Wales—which was founded in 1949 specifically to train engineers, scientists, and technologists and to initiate fundamental and applied research. Its Foundation Professors of Applied

Chemistry and Chemical Engineering were Professor A. E. Alexander and Professor (later Sir Philip) Baxter, respectively.

The establishment of the new universities and a more liberal financial policy engendered by the adoption of the Murray Report on Australian Universities by the Menzies Government in November 1957 gave a tremendous impetus to fundamental chemical research in Australia. A few large industrial firms also had research laboratories, where applied and fundamental research was pursued. However, financial restrictions since 1974 have forced the closure of many of these research laboratories, e.g. within NSW, the research laboratory of the Museum of Applied Arts and Sciences, Ultimo, where research on eucalyptus oils and natural products had been carried out for nearly a century; the Colonial Sugar Refining Company's research unit at Roseville; and the Roache Research Institute of Marine Pharmacology at Dee Why.

The public's enthusiasm for science and governments' attitude to scientific research has changed since the halcyon days of the early sixties. Chemical research, like other scientific research, requires more sophisticated equipment and is becoming increasingly expensive. Furthermore, Government funding is becoming more difficult to obtain. However, if this country is to survive as a developed nation, it must spend more money on research and development. In 1920 the two countries with the highest standard of living were Australia and Argentina. Now Australia is ranked about 17th and Argentina does not rate. With short-sighted policies and neglect of scientific research and development, we can soon end up like Argentina.

Industrial research and development in Australia is on a much smaller scale than in other countries with a comparable population, such as Sweden, Belgium, and The Netherlands. The need for professional chemists should increase, since they are required by a wide range of scientific disciplines from cancer research to oceanography.